

Increasing Employee Performance through Digital Culture, Compensation, Career Development and Employee Resilience in PT. Janji Mulya Executive Learning

Citra Junika Siregar¹, Achmad Fajar Hendarman²

^{1,2}Institut Teknologi Bandung

ABSTRACT: PT Janji Mulya Executive Learning (PT Janji Mulya) was a business unit within Janji Mulya Business School foundation and became an independent business entity as a limited liability company (Perseroan Terbatas) in January 2020. When Covid-19 happened, the company's revenue dropped to only 30% in the first year (2020) after the spin-off. In the next year (2021) the revenue increased almost one hundred percent despite the fact that it was still forty percent below the 2019 performance. The company expect that the trend will keep going up to the 2022 fiscal year, however the fact says the contrary: the revenue in 2022 was slightly going down. Besides, the majority of individual performance decreased by 45.9% of employees. These problems in the postpandemic condition that is differed from expectation, has raised concern of PT Janji Mulya management. Further information were obtained that several factors could be the cause of low employee performance, namely digital culture, compensation, career development, and employee resilience. Based on these problems, this research was conducted to know and analyze the relationship of digital culture, compensation, career development, and employee resilience, with employee performance, as well as to propose solution regarding the four factors that could increase employee performance.

To that end, this study was conducted with two objectives, namely descriptive and verification purpose. To analyse the hypotheses, this study employs multiple regression. Data collection was done by census to the population of PT Janji Mulya employees (N=60). Questionnaire was distributed at one-shot time horizon method and cross-sectional data.

The findings revealed that there is a significant simultaneous influence of the four independent variables on employee performance. The test of partial effect showed that each variable of digital culture, compensation, career development, and employee resilience, have a positive and significant relationship with employee performance.

Based on the results of the analysis that combines the results of hypothesis testing and the results of interviews with research informants, the business solutions for developing employee performance at PT Janji Mulya are arranged in the form of priorities based on the correlation values of the four variables on employee performance. Besides there are several insights that might influence employee performance, namely: a clear business strategy that is communicated effectively from the top management to the lowest level in the organization, Availability of resources that affect the performance of a department, and Strategic Foresight Analysis training to equip employees to be skillful at analyzing conditions, predicting changes that may occur, and managing response preparation and implementation plans, so that employees become more resilient.

KEYWORDS: Compensation, Career development, Digital culture, Employee resilience, Employee performance.

INTRODUCTION

PT. Janji Mulya Executive Learning (PT. Janji Mulya) was a business unit within Janji Mulya Business School foundation and became an independent business entity as a limited liability company (Perseroan Terbatas) in January 2020. The foundation decided to spin off PT. Janji Mulya to support it to become more flexible, agile, competitive, faster, and bigger. The spin-off however completed only two months before the Covid-19 pandemic outbreak hit the world. When it happened, the outbreak was disrupted a lot of industries, including training & consulting business. The company's revenue dropped to only 30% in the first year (2020) after the spin-off. In the next year (2021) the revenue increased almost one hundred percent despite the fact that it was still forty percent below the 2019 performance. The company expect that the trend will keep going up to the 2022 fiscal year, however the fact says the contrary: the revenue in 2022 was slightly going down.

The company performance and employee performance in this post-pandemic condition that is differed from expectation, has raised concern of PT. Janji Mulya ELI (PT. Janji Mulya) management. Through interview with several representatives of management and employees, information was obtained that one of the factors causing the company's low performance was employee performance. A study by Abdulkadir et al. (2012) showed that career planning systems have a significant effect on employee commitment to work. The same thing was found in the research of Tabiu and Nura (2019). Lartey (2021: 135) also states that "career planning was identified as a better contributor to engagement."

Meanwhile, Sitopu et al. (2021) revealed that one of the factors that affect performance is compensation. This is also supported by the research results of Nor (2018) and Saman (2020). The three studies revealed that compensation has a significant effect on performance. In addition, other studies reveal the importance of culture for improving employee performance. Strengers et al. (2022) show that top managers and employees have different perspectives on what culture improvement should have.

On the other hand, the environment is constantly changing and demands adaptability. At the organizational level, Rochet et al. (2008) said that crisis situations can offer decision makers and public organizations strategic levers to manage change in organizations and increase organizational resilience in facing crises. Organizations have no choice but to be resilient in the face of crises. Resilience implies the ability to bounce back after shock or disruption and to develop certain new capabilities for the organization.

At the employee level as a person, for example as a salesperson, Meintjes and Hofmeyr (2018) reveal that as a personal resource, a high level of toughness is needed for sales people to be successful and develop.

Based on this background and in order to generate business solution to increase employee performance as the main intention of this research, researcher at first, need to make sure whether those variables (Digital Culture, Compensation, Career Development, and Employee Resilience) have positive and significant relationship with Employee Performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. The relationship between digital culture and employee performance

Abdullahi et al. (2021) found that Organizational Culture has a significant effect on Employee performance. Similar findings were obtained in Sugiharjo's research (2019). In addition, according to Setiono et al. (2022), organizational culture has a close relationship with employee performance because organizational culture is an important factor in supporting the achievement of organizational goals. Similar findings found in by Nasution et al. (2018) that career development and organizational culture affect employee performance.

Goran et al. (2017) noted the results of the 2016 McKinsey survey that cultural and behavioral challenges are the most significant challenges in achieving digital priorities. Therefore, executives must be proactive in shaping and measuring culture, approaching it with the same rigor and discipline with which they tackle operational transformations. It includes changing the structural and tactical elements within the organization as opposed to the cultural change one seeks to achieve. The critical cultural intervention points identified by respondents to the 2016 digital survey were risk aversion, customer focus, and silos as being valuable roadmaps for leaders seeking to persist in reshaping their organizational culture.

B. The relationship between compensation and employee performance

Hoque et al. (2018) investigate the impact of the compensation system on employee performance. They were using quantitative analysis through survey as well as perceptions of 200 employees working in telecommunication service providers in Bangladesh. The study found that the compensation system has a significant positive effect on employee performance.

Syahreza et al. (2017) found something similar where compensation had a significant positive effect on the performance of hotel employees in Medan City. Compensation also affects employee satisfaction and employee performance at PT. Telecommunications Indonesia (Darma & Supriyanto, 2018). The same thing was revealed in Ramli's research (2018) at a private hospital in Jakarta.

C. The relationship between career development and employee performance

The results of Abdulkadir et al. (2012) research indicate that performance appraisal system, career planning system and employee participation significantly influence employee job commitment. Ali et al. (2019) found that career development and performance appraisal mediated the relationship between succession planning and employee performance. Similar findings found in by Nasution et al. (2018) that career development and organizational culture affect employee performance.

D. The relationship between employee resilience and employee performance

A coherent set of HR practices that enhance resilience has the potential to contribute to psychological capital, employee attitudes and behavior, and organizational performance not only in turbulent circumstances but also during periods of relative calm. Formal resilience training should be seen as a single component of a broader and coherent set of resilience-building HR practices. (Bardoel et al., 2014).

Suratman et al. (2021) also revealed that self-resilience has a positive and significant effect on performance. The same thing is proven by Burhanuddin (2022) who revealed that there is a significant influence from resilience on employee performance.

Based on the results of the studies above, a conceptual framework is compiled as follows:

Figure 1. Conceptual Model

Based on the conceptual model, the following hypotheses are developed:

1. Digital culture has positive and significant relationship with employee performance.
2. Compensation has positive and significant relationship with employee performance.
3. Career development has positive and significant relationship with employee performance.
4. Employee resilience has positive and significant relationship with employee performance.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research has a verification purpose. According to Sekaran (2010), verification research aims to reveal the relationship between variables. Data collection is done by census, which is taking all members of the population to be studied. In this case, the population is all of Janji Mulya Executive Learning Institute employees (N=60). Questionnaire to be distributed to all leaders and staff. This research was conducted using one-shot time horizon method and cross-sectional data.

This study employs multiple regression to analyse the hypotheses. Multiple regression is a statistical technique that is used to examine the relationship between a single dependent variable and several independent variables. The objective of multiple regression analysis is to use the independent variables whose values are known to predict the value of the single dependent value.

RESULT

A. Multiple Regression Analysis

1.1 Regression Coefficient

Regression analysis is used to measure the influence between the independent variables and the dependent variable. Multiple linear regression is a regression model that involves more than one independent variable and is carried out to find out the direction and how much influence the independent variables have on the dependent variable (Ghozali, 2018).

Table 1. Multiple Linear Regression Coefficient

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	13,137 ,173	1,643		7,998	,000
	DC	,176	,050	,336	3,491	,001
	COMP	,091	,082	,205	2,138	,037
	CD	,356	,041	,252	2,255	,028
	ER		,143	,231	2,487	,016

a. Dependent Variable: EP

The table above describes the regression analysis using the SPSS program, the equation model is as follows:

$$EP = 13.137 + 0.173DC + 0.176COMP + 0.091CD + 0.356ER + ei$$

The multiple linear regression equation above can be explained as follows:

The constant value (a) has a positive value of 13.137. The positive sign means that it shows a unidirectional influence between the independent variables and the dependent variable (Employee Performance). This shows that if all independent variables do not change, then the average Employee Performance is 13.137.

1.2 Simultaneous Testing (F-Test)

The F test is used to see the overall effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable. Thus, it can be seen whether each independent variable has a joint effect on the dependent variable. The results of the F test are obtained as follows:

Table 2. Simultaneous Testing

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	869,703	4	217,426	44,090	,000 ^a
	Residual	271,230	55	4,931		
	Total	1140,933	59			

a. Predictors: (Constant), ER, COMP, DC, CD

b. Dependent Variable: EP

Source: SPSS Output Results, 2022

The results of the assessment carried out with the SPSS program, obtained a value of F = 44.090 with sig. = 0.000 smaller than α of 0.05. This means that there is a significant simultaneous influence of the four independent variables on Employee Performance.

1.3 Partial Test (t test)

The t test is used to test the partial effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable. In addition, based on the t value, it can be obtained which variable has the strongest influence on the dependent variable. Table 1 above shows the regression coefficients of each independent variable having a sig probability value. $<\alpha$ (= 0.05) This means that Digital culture, Compensation, Career Development and Employee Resilience have a Positive and Significant Relationship with Employee Performance.

- a. Digital culture (DC) has a regression coefficient of 0.173 and significant Employee Performance where the t count is 3,491 greater than t table (1,672) and sig 0.001 α (0.05), so hypothesis 1 is accepted.
- b. Compensation (COMP) has a regression coefficient of 0.176 and significant Employee Performance where the t count is 2.138 greater than t table (1.672) and sig 0.0371 α (0.05), so hypothesis 2 is accepted.
- c. Career development (CD) has a regression coefficient of 0.091 and significant Employee Performance where the t count is 2.255 greater than t table (1.672) and sig 0.028 α (0.05), so hypothesis 3 is accepted.
- d. Employee resilience (ER) has a regression coefficient of 0.356 and significant Employee Performance where the t count is 2.487 greater than t table (1.672) and sig 0.016 α (0.05), so hypothesis 4 is accepted.

B. Coefficient of Determination (R²)

The coefficient of determination (R²) is used to measure the model's capacity to explain model variability. The results of the coefficient (R²) are as follows:

Table 3. Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	,873 ^a	,762	,745	2,22069	1,861

a. Predictors: (Constant), ER, COMP, DC, CD

b. Dependent Variable: EP

The results of calculating the R² value obtained in the R² research model is 0.762, meaning that 76.2% of the variation in Employee Performance can be explained by the four independent variables, while the remaining 23.8% is explained by other factors outside the research model.

DISCUSSION

A. Relationship between digital culture and employee performance

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it is known that digital culture has a significant relationship with employee performance. The results of testing the first hypothesis are in line with the results of Abdullahi et al. (2021), Sugiharjo (2019), Setiono et al. (2022), and Nasution et al. (2018).

Gavric et al. (2016) said that the impact of organizational culture can be felt across all aspects of the business, which is reflected in the final results. Goran et al. (2017) stated that deficiencies in organizational culture are one of the main obstacles to company success in the digital era. There are three drawbacks of digital culture: functional and departmental silos, a fear of taking risks, and difficulty forming and acting on a single view of the customer. Organizations that focus on transforming culture and building capabilities during a transformation are 2.5 times more likely to succeed.

PT. Janji Mulya tried to explore digital culture and digital operations from decision makers to operations. Although it takes time, Company is already aware that digital is important for business continuity, but the challenge is that they need to change habits so that digital execution has an impact on the company. Management needs to have an awareness of the extent of readiness to implement digital culture. There must be a mature strategy to apply digitalization.

Companies need time to implement digital culture and digital operations from the decision maker level to the operational department. So, cultural transformation efforts towards digital culture are still ongoing. Internally, there are needs to be innovative and fast to adapt to the changes that occur in the training and education industry. The company is willing, but the problem is how to establish collaboration between each division. Meanwhile, engagement with new people has not been well established, coupled with for example new policies that have not been informed due to several limitations that hinder employee performance.

B. Relationship between compensation and employee performance

The results of hypothesis testing show that compensation has a significant relationship between compensation and employee performance at PT. Janji Mulya. Mello (2015) said that compensation can increase employee commitment. With commitment, employees will try their best to carry out their duties so as to affect their performance.

Management is very supportive. In terms of monthly salary, it is perceived as sufficient, but other variables still need to be improved. In addition, changes in activities due to the pandemic have reduced several incentives, such as no official travel expenses. Giving bonuses are not transparent based on a certain calculation or a certain percentage of sales. The culture at Prasmul is kinship and the leader is not a transactional type.

This is a challenge faced at PT. Janji Mulya, namely how to balance the family culture with the clarity of the bonus system that can encourage performance in the sales department in particular. Clarity in the calculation of the incentive or bonus system is expected to motivate employees to achieve targets. This is as evidenced in the results of the research by Hoque et al. (2018), Shahreza et al. (2017), Darma & Supriyanto (2018), and Ramli that the compensation system has a significant positive effect on employee performance. Likewise, it is proven in the results of hypothesis testing in this study that compensation has a significant effect on employee performance.

C. Relationship between career development and employee performance

The results of hypothesis testing show that career development has a significant relationship with employee performance at PT. Janji Mulya. This is in line with the findings of Abdulkadir et al. (2012), Ali et al. (2019), and Nasution et al. (2018) that career development and organizational culture affect employee performance.

Meanwhile, career opportunities at PT. Janji Mulya are not as big as in other companies with a long and wide corporate structure. Under these conditions, the career opportunity is not too high. Moreover, demographically, it can be said that many employees are quite young. The opportunity for replacement in a higher position will take a long time, which is around 10 to 20 years. However, remuneration can still grow.

D. Relationship antara employee resilience dengan employee performance

The test results show that employee resilience has a significant relationship with employee performance. This is in line with the results of Bardoel et al. (2014), Suratman et al. (2021), and Burhanuddin (2022). Resilience was defined as an individual's capacity to respond to adversity at work in a way that strengthens and develops himself as a better person, and comprises the four potential dimensions identified above: perseverance, positive emotion, meaning making and commitment to growth (Amir and Standen, 2019). These four aspects are proven to contribute to employee performance.

Employee resilience at PT. Janji Mulya is also formed because of the value that grows within the company, namely kinship. High tolerance and mutual help play a significant role in keeping employees at PT. Janji Mulya even in declining conditions. Although there are still employees who still rely on superiors in solving problems related to clients. So, what needs to be improved is the ability to solve problems, while on the customer focus side it is already good.

In 2020 and 2021, employees experienced a lack of bonuses and salary increases but the turnover rate was still good, which is still below 20%. This is because engagement with the company has been built. So, even though employees receive offers from other companies, they still stay at PT. Janji Mulya. They think that if they stay and survive, the company will also survive.

Regarding employee resilience, it has been considered at the beginning of the recruitment process. At the time of employee recruitment, there is a psychological test to measure how resilient and endurance the employees are in facing challenges. Then with experience in dealing with clients and difficult situations, it will also increase employee resilience. High resilience can make employees able to overcome problems and try to find new solutions and innovations to maintain their performance.

E. Proposed Business Solution

The business solutions for developing employee performance at PT. Janji Mulya are arranged in the form of priorities based on the correlation values of the four variables on employee performance. The test results show that the four variables simultaneously and partially correlate well with employee performance. Partially, employee resilience has the highest loading factor on employee performance, namely 0.356, followed by compensation (0.176), digital culture (0.173), and career development (0.091). This indicates that employee resilience is the variable that has the most dominant role in establishing employee performance at PT. Janji Mulya. Therefore, priority is given to developing employee performance starting from developing employee resilience, followed by compensation, digital culture, and career development. Alternative solutions for developing employee resilience are presented in Table 4.11.

Table 4. Development of Employee Resilience

Aspect	Current Condition	Improvement design
Perseverance	There are employees who still need to be assisted in solving problems in dealing with difficult clients	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Encouraging employees to be able to face difficulties by continuing to try and have strong self-discipline. - Efforts to direct employees to have problem solving skills and be able to make their own decisions in the technical matters.
Positive emotions	There are employees who still need to be assisted in solving problems when conditions are down	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continue to guide employees to maintain a positive outlook in the face of difficulties and declining conditions.
Meaning making	Employees need to be mentally improved in dealing with hectic and overloaded conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Encouraging employees to be able to actively reflect and affirm personal values when faced with problems.
Commitment to growth	In difficult times, employee turnover is still below 20%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Encourage and empower employees to have hope and become stronger during times of intense downturn and the loss of control, by establishing trust and effective communication vertically and horizontally across sections. Establish the reliable management team that walk the talk.

Alternative compensation development solutions are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Compensation Development

Aspect	Current Condition	Improvement design
Basic Pay	Basic pay is considered sufficient by employees with a standard that exceeds other companies engaged in the education business	Increase basic pay according to company growth
Overtime Allowance	Currently, the company has provided overtime for office staff positions. Supervisors and above do not receive overtime. For certain departments such as studio/production, they are not given overtime, but instead are replaced off-day	Implement overtime cash calculation in accordance with applicable Labor regulations/Law, and socialize and ensure employees in positions that do not receive overtime understand and accept positively the existing rules of the game.
Bonus	There is no transparency in giving bonuses regarding the calculation of the percentage of bonuses compared to revenue or employee achievement	Formulate a bonus system with a transparent scheme, especially for the sales department to boost enthusiasm in finding new clients
Travel/Accommodation Allowance	There are some disappointments of the insufficient amount of the allowance due to the raising of inflation rate	Reviewing the travel/accommodation allowance scheme
Medical Allowance	Health insurance is a form of compensation given to employees, however some employees perceive it as insufficient due to the raising of inflation rate	Maintain and/or increase the provision of medical allowances in accordance with government policies and company conditions

Alternative solutions for developing digital culture are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Digital Culture Development

Aspect	Current Condition	Improvement design
Calculated risk	Companies are already aware of the importance of digital, but it takes time and consideration of several aspects of transforming to digital so that it becomes a habit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Encouraging employees' willingness to experiment with new things in relation to digitalization. - Encouraging the willingness of employees to continue to be able to adapt to developments in digital technology that can be utilized to produce solutions to possible risks that arise. - Encouraging employees to want to invest in new fields that can support increasing knowledge - Encouraging a change in mindset about risk, that risks can be turned into opportunities. Like the Covid-19 pandemic, it has increased the growth of online training in various fields. - Encouraging the mindset that everyone can become an ambassador for the company, not just salespeople in order to deal with general situations or difficult situations faced by clients - Digital innovation needs to be developed to encourage employees to be able to explore new programs that are more attractive to the current market, which tends to avoid the best price program.
Customer focus	Employee customer focus is good, so is employee competency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Digital data management needs to be continuously developed - Development of tools that make it easier for clients and prospective clients to interact with the company - Development of integration between structured data and unstructured data - Improve data refresh implementation to update data according to current conditions and to filter data that is still needed and data that is obsolete and no longer needed
Busting silo	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Companies are still adapting to digitalization where one another requires collaboration. - When switching to digital, there are challenges in creating engagement among employees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop a system that can make it easier for employees to get information - Increase the internal data transparency - Develop the implementation of management rotation

Alternative career development solutions are presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Development of Career Development

Aspect	Current Condition	Improvement design
Organization centered planning system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is an addition of personnel - The career tree is not very high - Replacement for a position at a higher level requires a relatively long time 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improve the implementation of Human Resources development needs - Improve the HR quality improvement programs - Improve the career path clarity - Improve the ability to assess individual potential on job evaluation - Improve the ability of employees in developing the harmonization of organizational needs and careers - Increase the implementation of career counseling about work and quality of life - Improve the audit implementation and control of career planning and development systems
Person centered planning system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is an open opportunity for employees to submit what is expected. - Employees have opportunities for personal development - Employees find it difficult to ask for mentoring regarding career advancement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase the ability to identify individual potential, skills and interests - Increase the ability to identify life goals and career goals - Improve the ability in preparing written plans to achieve individual goals - Improve the ability in researching or searching and getting the best career start - Increase the ability to communicate career plans directly to individuals by their managers - Increase the support from mentors or sponsors to employees - Improve the ability of employees to promote self-image or recognition of employee quality

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

A. Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to find out and analyze the relationship between digital culture, compensation, career development, and employee resilience on employee performance at PT. Janji Mulya. Based on the research results, it can be concluded as follows:

1. Digital culture has positive and significant relationship with employee performance.
2. Compensation has positive and significant relationship with employee performance.
3. Career development has positive and significant relationship with employee performance.
4. Employee resilience has positive and significant relationship with employee performance.
5. Because the four variables are positively and significantly correlated with employee performance, proposed business solutions can be produced regarding the four factors above to increase employee performance.

B. Recommendation

Based on the calculation of R² in the research model, the results show that R² value is 0.762, meaning that 76.2% of the variation in Employee Performance can be explained by the four independent variables, while the remaining 23.8% is explained by other factors outside the research model. Therefore, the researcher recommends PT. Janji Mulya to conduct further research to investigate other factors that also affect employee performance.

From the results of the interviews, there are several insights obtained that might influence employee performance, such as:

1. A clear business strategy that is communicated effectively from the top management to the lowest level in the organization.

2. Availability of resources that affect the performance of a department, for example: Sales people can increase sales revenue through consultant's new skills development, to fulfill the customer's need that is growing.
3. Strategic Foresight Analysis training to equip employees to be skillful at analyzing conditions, predicting changes that may occur, managing response preparation and implementation plan, so that employees become more resilient because resilience has the highest correlation with employee performance) and perform excellently.

REFERENCES

1. Abdulkadir, D. S., Isiaka, S. B., & Adedoyin, S. I. (2012). Effects of strategic performance appraisal, career planning and employee participation on organizational commitment: An empirical study. *International Business Research*, 5(4), 124.
2. Abdullahi, M., Raman, K., & Solarin, S. (2021). Effect of organizational culture on employee performance: A mediating role of employee engagement in Malaysia educational sector. *International Journal of Supply and Operations Management*, 8(3), 232-246.
3. Ali, Z., Mahmood, B., & Mehreen, A. (2019). Linking succession planning to employee performance: The mediating roles of career development and performance appraisal. *Australian Journal of Career Development*, 28(2), 112-121.
4. Altındağ, E., & Köseadağı, Y. (2015). The relationship between emotional intelligence of managers, innovative corporate culture and employee performance. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 210, 270-282
5. Amir, M. T., & Standen, P. (2019). Growth-focused resilience: development and validation of a new scale. *Management Research Review*, 42(6), 681-702. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MRR-04-2018-0151>
6. Bardoel, E. A., Pettit, T. M., De Cieri, H., & McMillan, L. (2014). Employee resilience: An emerging challenge for HRM. *Asia Pacific Journal of Human Resources*, 52(3), 279-297.
7. Bedarkar, M., & Pandita, D. (2014). A study on the drivers of employee engagement impacting employee performance. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 133, 106-115.
8. Burhanuddin, B. (2022). The Effect of Achievement-Motivation-Training, Religiosity, and Resilience on Employee Performance. *Quantitative Economics and Management Studies*, 3(4), 661-666.
9. Dessler, G. (2000). *Human Resource Management*. 8th Edition. Prentice-Hall. Inc: Upper Saddle River, New Jersey
10. Friborg, O., Hjemdal, O., Rosenvinge, J., & Martinussen, M. (2003). A new rating scale for adult resilience: What are the central prospective resources behind healthy adjustment? *International Journal of Methods in Psychiatric Research*, 12(2), 65-76
11. Gavrić, G., Sormaz, G., & Ilić, Đ. (2016). The impact of organizational culture on the ultimate performance of a company. *International Review*, (3-4), 25-30.
12. Ghazali, I. (2011). "Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate Dengan Program SPSS". Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro
13. Ghazali, I. (2016). *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate Dengan Program IBM SPSS 23 (Edisi 8)*. Cetakan ke VIII. Semarang : Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
14. Ghazali, I. (2018). *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate dengan Program IBM SPSS*. 25. Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro
15. Goran, J., LaBerge, L., and Srinivasan, R. (2017). *Culture for a digital age*. McKinsey Quarterly.
16. Hall, D. W., & Wayne, M. L. (2013). Ohno's "peril of hemizygosity" revisited: gene loss, dosage compensation, and mutation. *Genome biology and evolution*, 5(1), 1-15.
17. Hall, D. W., & Wayne, M. L. (2013). Ohno's "peril of hemizygosity" revisited: gene loss, dosage compensation, and mutation. *Genome biology and evolution*, 5(1), 1-15.
18. Hendarman, A.F. & Pangestu, A.B. (2021). *Manajemen Modal Insani Kontemporer*. ITB Press,
19. Herbert, M. (2011). *An exploration of the relationships between psychological capital (hope, optimism, self-efficacy, resilience), occupational stress, burnout and employee engagement* (Doctoral dissertation, Stellenbosch: Stellenbosch University).
20. Hoque, A. S. M. M., Awang, Z., Siddiqui, B. A., & Sabiu, M. S. (2018). Role of employee engagement on compensation system and employee performance relationship among telecommunication service providers in Bangladesh. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 8(3), 19-37.

21. Hughes, R.L., Ginnet, R.C., Curphy, G.J. (2015). Leadership: enhancing the lessons of experience. 8th edition. McGrawHill International Edition.
22. Jew, C.L., Green, K.E., & Kroger, J. (1999). Development and validation of a measure of resiliency. *Measurement and Evaluation in Counselling and Development*, 32(2), 75-89.
23. Juliandi, A., Irfan, Manurung, S. (2014). Metodologi. Penelitian Bisnis: Konsep dan Aplikasi. Medan: UMSU Press.
24. Karaimak, O. (2010). Establishing the psychometric qualities of the Connor–Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC) using exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis in a trauma survivor sample. *Psychiatry Research*, 179(3), 350–356.
25. Lartey, F. M. (2021). Impact of career Planning, employee autonomy, and manager recognition on employee engagement. *Journal of Human Resource and Sustainability Studies*, 9(02), 135.
26. Manolescu, A. (2003) *Human Resource Management*, 4th Edition, The Economic Publishing House, Bucarest, p.332
27. McGrath, R. G. (2013). The end of competitive advantage: How to keep your strategy moving as fast as your business. Harvard Business Review Press
27. Meintjes, A., & Hofmeyr, K. (2018). The impact of resilience and perceived organisational support on employee engagement in a competitive sales environment. *SA Journal of Human Resource Management*, 16(1), 1-11.
28. Mello, J.A. (2015) *Strategic Human Resource Management*, 4th Edition, Cengage Learning
29. Mihardjo, L.WW. (2020). “Budaya Perusahaan di Era Digital berbasis Co-creation-Innovation”, In book: *Strategic Management in Digital Era: Revisited concept and Findings* (pp.187-215). DRM Alumni
30. Mondy, R. W., Robert M. N., dan Shane R. P. (1993). *Human Resource Management*. Fifth Edition. Massachusetts: Allyn and Bacon.
31. Mondy, R. W., Robert M. N., dan Shane R. P. (1993). *Human Resource Management*. Fifth Edition. Massachusetts: Allyn and Bacon.
32. Nasution, F. N., Mariatin, E., & Zahreni, S. (2018). The influence of career development and organizational culture on employee performance. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management*, 6(01), 57-65.
33. Nor, A. I. (2018). Enhancing employee performance through human resource management practices: a review of literature. *European Journal of Human Resource Management Studies*.
34. Pangastuti, P. A. D., Sukirno, S., & Efendi, R. (2020). The Effect of Work Motivation and Compensation on Employee Performance. *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding*, 7(3), 292-299.
35. Ramli, A. H. (2018). Compensation, job satisfaction and employee performance in health services. *Business and Entrepreneurial Review*, 18(2), 177-186.
36. Rochet, C., Keramidis, O., & Bout, L. (2008). Crisis as change strategy in public organizations. *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 74(1), 65-77.
37. Saleem, S., & Amin, S. (2013). The impact of organizational support for career development and supervisory support on employee performance: An empirical study from Pakistani academic sector. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 5(5), 194-207.
38. Saman, A. (2020). Effect of compensation on employee satisfaction and employee performance. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting Research (IJEBAR)*, 4(01).
39. Santoso, S. (2000). *Buku Latihan SPSS Statistik Parametrik*. Jakarta: PT Elex. Media Komputindo.
40. Sekaran, U. (2010). *Research Methods for Business: A Skill-Building Approach*. 4th Edition, John Wiley & Sons
41. Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2017). *Metode penelitian untuk bisnis: Pendekatan pengembangan–keahlian*. Jakarta Selatan: Salemba Empat
42. Setiono, R., Elmi, F., & Rimawan, E. (2022). Digital Transformation As Intervening Variable On The Effect Of Leadership, Competence And Organizational Culture On Employee Performance (Case Study: Dpu Bank Indonesia). *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 2672-2681.
43. Sinclair, V.G., & Wallston, K.A. (2004). The development and psychometric evaluation of the Brief Resilient Coping Scale. *Assessment*, 11(1), 94-101
44. Sitopu, Y. B., Sitinjak, K. A., & Marpaung, F. K. (2021). The Influence of Motivation, Work Discipline, and Compensation on Employee Performance. *Golden Ratio of Human Resource Management*, 1(2), 72-83.

45. Strengers, J., Mutsaers, L., Van Rossum, L., & Graamans, E. (2022). The organizational culture of scale-ups and performance. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 35(8), 115-130.
46. Sugiharjo, R. J. (2019). The Influence of Organizational Culture, and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance (Case Study on Digital Printing).
47. Sugiyono. (2010). *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan Pendekatan Kuantitatif, kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
48. Suratman, A., Suhartini, S., Palupi, M., Dihan, F. N., & Muhlison, M. B. (2021). The Impact of Psychological Climate and Self-Resilience on Employee Performance During the COVID-19 Pandemic: An Empirical Study in Indonesia. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 8(5), 1019-1029.
49. Syahreza, D. S., Lumbanraja, P., Dalimunthe, R. F., & Absah, Y. (2017). Compensation, employee performance, and mediating role of retention: A study of differential semantic scales.
50. Tabiu, A., & Nura, A. A. (2020). Assessment of Career Planning as Predictor of Employee Performance: The Role of Perceived Career Opportunity. *Sains Humanika*, 12(2).
51. Wagnild, G.M., & Young, H.M. (1990). Resilience among older women. *Journal of Nursing Scholarship*, 22(4), 252-255
52. Welbourne, Theresa M., Diana E. Johnson, Amir Erez, (1998). the role-based performance scale. *Academy of Management Journal*, 41(5).

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